

1 **Characterization of ATP-binding cassettes (membrane channels functioning as pumps) activated**
2 **in partial response in humans with cancer.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We compared total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with breast cancer comparing tumors
8 based on complete response or partial response in the patient to perform comprehensive discovery of
9 genes functioning in multi-drug resistance behavior in vivo. The genes we discovered with increased
10 expression in the tumors of humans with failed or partial responses included Abca3, Abcb7 and Abcb8,
11 Abce1 and Abcf1 and Abcf3. Recurrent correlation of Abcc5 with failed treatment was observed. Abcc5
12 may possess strong resistance-imparting quality and its expression is enriched in the tumors of humans
13 with resistance to chemotherapy.
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28